

Next Generation Intelligent Spaces

Abstract—A building equipped with sensors is a use case of heterogeneous data sources distributed naturally across spaces or zones. Lack of spatiotemporal awareness can lead to excessive sensors or non-optimal distribution across a building. We extend the problem of optimal sensor placement to find the minimal sensor group that can robustly approximate the rest of the sensors values. The solution uses a distributed learning step to parallelize the predictive capability of candidate groups generated by evolutionary computing techniques. Additionally, the system models the cost and energy consumption of the sensor group when performing a multi-objective optimization. We experiment on 24 zones from a seven-storied building in Thailand to establish a trade-off between virtualization accuracy, energy footprint, and installation cost. The work exploits the concept of "less is more" to bring down the capital and recurring expense for a smart building solution.

Index Terms—smart buildings, ambient intelligence, sensor optimization, business intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

The know-how of designing and making buildings has seen tumultuous scales of updates as seen from huts to skyscrapers. Before the advent the electricity, the buildings were conceived as a mere brick and mortar rendition for habitable and workable spaces. When electrical appliances started populating households, the notion of passive space turned into a controllable environment using sensors and actuators. However, most of the existing buildings were already constructed before the apparition of internet and world wide web in 1990. This means building architectures were not developed keeping in mind the quantity, type and location of sensors. The popularity of Internet of Thing (IoT) devices have lead to an ad-hoc assimilation in buildings that are usually situated in an environment of dynamic parameters like temperature, CO2, wind, etc. Such an approach can lead to naive zonal distribution of sensors due to obscurity on spatio-temporal

importance. Secondly, a streaming IoT sensor can act as a data source of sensitive patterns raising privacy concerns among stakeholders. Thirdly, the cost of equipping spaces with embedded hardware over a large commercial space is non-negligible and comes with a recurring payment of powering up the solution. In this work, we investigate if there is a way to determine a minimalist sensing solution for non-intrusive spatio-temporal coverage to lower the capital cost and energy footprint for a smart building solution.

Problem Setting. Let there be Z locations in a building that are equipped with no more than K types of sensors. We seek to find the optimal bipartite set of sensors coupled with a knowledge base to predict any one of the two sets using the other. Let \mathcal{H}^g represent the collective knowledge of a group g that can contain multiple ambient sensors and power meters. $\mathcal{H} = \{\mathcal{H}^g | \forall g \in G\}$ is built in a way to provide a predictive coverage over all Z zones with G logical partitions of sensors. Then $Z \cap \mathcal{H}$ shall be semantically interpreted as the subset of spaces that are equipped with sensors. So $\mathcal{H} - (Z \cap \mathcal{H})$ denotes the approximated knowledge of $Z \cap \mathcal{H}$ sensor-less zones.

The problem is to find the minimal working subset of sensors ($Z \cup \mathcal{H}$) to yield the best hypothesis space \mathcal{H}^* with least prediction error. The set \mathcal{H}^* is termed as **virtual sensor field** because of its capability to replace an embedded hardware with a software approximation of the same.

In the upcoming sections we explain the context and motivation for the problem and formulate a distributed scalable solution. Then, we study experimentally the effect of distinct semantic groupings on the virtualization accuracy, followed by a multi-objective optimization to discover the minimal sensor group. Finally we compare our results with a state of art work in optimal sensor placement to highlight key differences between the two types of problem.

II. RELATED WORK

Historically, buildings were not designed to cater to forms of ambient intelligence rather optimized spatially for acceptable levels of thermal comfort, indoor ventilation, and privacy. With the passage of time, building became a composite of observable and controllable elements.

A. Review of Technology Acceptance

Smart applications [1] for buildings has been developed mainly for monitoring, analysis, and control of thermal units like Heating Ventilation Air Conditioning (HVAC) units, illumination channels etc. A 2019 review [2] of the smart building industry states the major pain points towards technological adaption. High installation costs, obscurity on data storage policies, and privacy concerns impede the acceptance [3] of Internet of Things in buildings. Typically a smart building applications thrive on real time sensor data for monitoring or actuation. Research shows that analysing sensor streams can reveal sensitive patterns about occupancy [4] or usage. Consequently, privacy becomes a major concern for occupants in a building due to a non zero possibility of data leak. The cost of constructing [5] a smart building is usually 1.2-1.8 times a non-smart counterpart. This initial capital poses the second barrier for a stake holder [6] to overcome before system installation. But before a technical deployment [7], the smart solution needs go through a pre-evaluation stage before finalizing the bill of materials.

We add to the literature a methodology for pre-integration, and initial planning with a market segmentation analysis. The motivation for a minimalist

sensor design aids to non-intrusive sensing that can either be ad-hocly assembled or composed with industrial grade sensors. The proposed system optimises logical grouping that encodes a human-interpretable data sharing policy.

B. Ambient Intelligence

Multiple cyber physical systems like sensors and actuators work in cohesion to maintain a desired quality of ambience and indoor comfort of a building. Some examples of non-intrusive ambient sensors are temperature, humidity, luminosity. Data values recorded by a type of sensor is usually dissimilar across different buildings or between separate zones in a building. Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) [8] of a continuous variable such as temperature, humidity or luminosity yields Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMF) [9]. This has been shown useful for structural health monitoring [10] for buildings. K means clustering over the space of IMF for all the sensors is shown to be effective [11] in identifying non identical sensors. This approach is further extended [12] by using information loss to eliminate weak candidate points from a cluster to obtain a solution to the Optimal Sensor Location Problem (OSLP). A key experimental insight of OSLP is that there can be more than one group, which are not worse from one another or Pareto Optimal [13] in nature.

We broaden the scope of the OSLP to find the minimal support sensors that can predict the redundant sensor values. The aim here is to generate a virtual sensor field for a building that is spatially optimised to have the least generalization error in prediction. For example, the behaviour of a group of temperature sensors situated across multiple zones probably can be learnt by an optimal fraction of embedded devices. Noticeably the energy footprint in powering up all sensors is higher than a fraction of the same.

III. VIRTUAL SENSOR FIELD

The key element in designing a distributed Virtual Sensor Field is to find the optimal group of sensors that can approximate the missing ones through data driven machine learning. The system evaluates the

error generated by the approximation on multiple operational objectives to yield a minimalist set of possible solutions. Each solution is then interpreted as a set of locations to place sensors along with their types.

A. Sensor Grouping

Let assume there are a maximum of K types of sensors in the building, which are grouped according to their nature like groups of temperature, humidity, power sensors etc. We will interpret the function $A^c(g)$ to fetch elements of a group g from a chromosome. So for a sensor-wise grouping, we set the access function $A^c(g) = A_s^c(g)$ for $g \in K$ groups as

$$A_s^c(g \in K) = \{e_z^g | \forall z \in Z\} \quad (1)$$

Spatial grouping of sensors is done by setting $A^c(g) = A_z^c(g)$ to partition the sensor set as shown in Equation 2.

$$A_z^c(g \in Z) = \{e_i^g | \forall i \in K\} \quad (2)$$

We construct **building chromosome** B^c as an aggregation of (G) logical groups such that $|B^c| = \sum_{g \in G} |A^c(g)|$ as per Equation 3. The 1D vector of 0's and 1's represent offline/missing or online status of sensors respectively and is constructed by appending $A^c(g)$ in any arbitrary fixed order of $g \in Z \vee K$.

$$B^c = \{e_1^i, e_2^i \dots e_K^i | \forall i \in G, e_j^i \in \{0, 1\}\} \quad (3)$$

B. Virtual Field

Within a group, the subgroup denoted by $\mathbf{0}$ encoding is treated as the approximation set A_g and the rest of sensors as support set S_g . The collective task for a group g is to learn the best mapping \mathcal{H}^* from $S_g \xrightarrow{\mathcal{H}^*} A_g$. The hypothesis space given by Equation composed of two parts, to support bidirectional mapping between sets $\{A_g, S_g\}$

$$\mathcal{H}^g = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{H}_f^g & : S_g \rightarrow A_g \\ \mathcal{H}_b^g & : A_g \rightarrow S_g \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

For the g^{th} group, we store a 2D **error matrix** M^g and a **library** \mathcal{H}^g of machine learnt functions, both of size $|A^c(g)|^2$. A function L is used to evaluate

the error in predicting channel $v \in A_g$ using a predictor with input $u \in S_g$ and records the loss in the $[u, v]^{th}$ cell of the error matrix as per Equation 5.

$$M^g[u, v] = L(v, \mathcal{H}^g[u, v](u)) \quad (5)$$

Note that $M^g[u, v] \neq M^g[v, u]$ implies that the two losses generated by swapping the dependent and independent variable may not be equal. To estimate the value y_v of a channel v that lies in group g , we first select up the optimal channel (u^*) to predict by using the $[u^*, v]^{th}$ entry of hypothesis library \mathcal{H}_f^g as per Equation 6.

$$\begin{aligned} u^* &\leftarrow \arg \min_{u \in A^c(g)} M^g[u, v] \\ y_v &= \mathcal{H}^g[u^*, v](u^*) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

This technique bounds the maximum observable error since it is not impossible that another optimal mapping \mathcal{H}^* can exist using more than one feature to map and yields better generalization.

$$L(A_g, \mathcal{H}^*(S_g)) \leq \sup_{u, v \in S_g, A_g} L(v, \mathcal{H}^i[u, v](u)) \quad (7)$$

The system parallel computes for all the groups to generate the hypothesis space and the error matrix table. Sequential execution returns the predictive power of a chromosome consisting of G logical groups in $O(|G|W^2)$ where $W = \sup_{g \in G} |A^c(g)|$.

C. Minimal Support Group

Next we proceed to find the minimal group that minimizes a set of l objectives $\mathbf{O} = [O_1, O_2, \dots O_l]$ to augment the virtual sensor field physically. This solution to such kind of problems is a set of 'non-inferior' solutions where any O_i can not be improved without increasing $O_j, j \neq i$. We define two objectives to measure the prediction error due to forward \mathcal{H}_f^g and backward \mathcal{H}_b^g hypothesis spaces by Equations 8 and 9 respectively.

$$O_f^v(B^c) = \sum_{g \in G} \sum_{v \in S_g} \sum_{u \in A_g} \left\{ \frac{M^g[\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}]}{|S_g A_g|} \right\} \quad (8)$$

$$O_b^v(B^c) = \sum_{g \in G} \sum_{v \in S_g} \sum_{u \in A_g} \left\{ \frac{M^g[\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u}]}{|S_g A_g|} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Next we model the monetary risk associated with a smart building solution as the total number of sensors in S_g , cost of the hardware solution

Fig. 1: Interaction between Support and Approximated Sets within a group of $m + n$ elements

and energy consumption of the same. Let there are two 1D vectors $P_g^w = \{pw_1, pw_2 \dots pw_k\}$ and $P_g^r = \{pr_1, pr_2 \dots pr_k\}$ to store the power consumption and purchase cost respectively. Correspondingly Equation 10 expresses the cost of implementing smartness in a building as the dot product of encoding and price vector. Similarly Equations 11 and 12 infer the number of sensors and power consumption for an arbitrarily encoded sequence respectively.

$$O_{cost} = \sum_{g \in G=Z} \langle A^c(g), P_g^r \rangle \quad (10)$$

$$O_{\#sens} = \sum_{g \in G=Z} \langle A^c(g), \vec{1} \rangle \quad (11)$$

$$O_{energy} = \sum_{g \in G=Z} \langle A^c(g), P_g^w \rangle \quad (12)$$

For a group, we penalize an encoding of all zeroes by Equation 13 since it means no sensors are reduced and the learnt hypothesis space is not used.

$$P(A^c(g)) = \begin{cases} \infty, & \text{if } A^c(g) = 0_{1 \times |A^c(g)|} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Figure 2 depicts the flow chart in which the system optimises the virtual sensor field with a

minimal group of sensors. We use NSGA II [14] to search the chromosomal vector space of $O(2^{KZ})$ to optimise our objectives.

- 1) Take as input the learnt hypothesis space and error matrix $\{\mathcal{H}^g, M^g\} \forall g \in G$.
- 2) Initialize a genetic pool (P_t) of chromosomes as a random string of 0's and 1's.
- 3) For every chromosome, evaluate the objective set $[O_f^v, O_b^v, O_{cost}, O_{\#sens}, O_{energy}]$.
- 4) If the maximum number of generations are reached or incremental gain is lower than a threshold the algorithm stops else a child population Q_t is created using steps 5, 6 and 7.
- 5) Non dominated sorting is used to incrementally identify Pareto optimal solutions till the entire population is exhausted.
- 6) Crowding Distance is used to check the density around individual solutions to prevent the algorithm for terminating in a local optima. In fact, chromosomes that fall within the rectangular field spanned by the nearest adjacent solutions are discarded.
- 7) Alteration in the encoding is achieved through genetic operators: Random Crossover and Mutation.
- 8) Now populations P_t and Q_t are combined to generate the parent population at time $t + 1$ using steps 5 and 6 in order.
- 9) Go back to Step 3 and iterate with generation count decreased by 1.

The algorithm terminates with a set of Pareto optimal solutions or minimal groups. We experimentally investigate the quality of these groups that can optimally power up the virtual sensor field.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

The data-set [15] comes from smart high-rise building in Thailand with 1.5 years of data collected at 1 minute resolution. We investigate 24 zones equipped with ambient sensors and power consumption meter. The analysis is presented in three parts : a) evaluate the accuracy of the virtual field with all sensors, b) understand the effect of removing sensors by comparing our algorithm with a baseline for the optimal sensor placement problem

Fig. 2: Sequence of Steps to Optimize the Virtual Sensor Field

c) understanding trade-offs in a multi objective optimization.

A. Virtualization Accuracy

To guess a sensor $v \in A^c(g)$, the system learn a set of supervised machine learnt predictors with a single channel data input $u \in A^c(g), u \neq v$. For every group, $O(|A^c(g)|^2)$ learners are trained to capture the intra group sensor dynamics. For a prediction task, a learner picks the least erred model from a set of classical algorithms: linear regression, lasso net, random forest, and XGBoost. Let for a group g the approximated (A_g) and ground truth are represented by vectors \hat{y}_s^z and y_s^z for sensor s at location z respectively. The mean squared error is given as

$$L_{MSE} = \frac{1}{KZ} \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{z \in Z} (\hat{y}_s^z - y_s^z)^2$$

(a) M^z where $z = \text{Floor 7 Zone 5}$

(b) M^z where $z = \text{Floor 4 Zone 1}$

Fig. 3: Error Matrix for 2 zones

First we check the effect of spatial grouping on the virtual sensor field accuracy. Variations in Figure 3 is explained by the fact that zone 5 is from top Floor 7 and experiences a harsher environment like direct sun light, higher temperature/humidity fluctuations than zone 1 of Floor 4. Figures 7 and 8 show the virtualization error for domain wise grouping as a heat-map covering all zones. We observe that AC Power bears a negative correlation with temperature and humidity when AC is turned on primarily for cooling. Light Power is positively related to indoor luminosity levels by observing at night the lights are off and during day, the lights are turned on for acceptable visibility levels. Power consumed due to appliances has an inverse affinity for temperature and humidity, which likely indicate working condi-

Zone	Power			Ambience		
	AC	Light	App	Temp	RH	Lux
Floor2Z1	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.18	0.53	0.15
Floor2Z2	0.08	0.07	0.15	0.11	0.36	0.06
Floor2Z4	0.33	0.31	0.73	0.33	0.66	0.31
Floor3Z1	0.32	0.23	0.38	0.24	0.45	0.26
Floor3Z2	0.35	0.25	0.27	0.29	0.4	0.27
Floor3Z4	0.34	0.23	0.25	0.22	0.61	0.22
Floor3Z5	0.42	0.25	0.27	0.28	0.63	0.24
Floor4Z1	0.28	0.24	0.19	0.2	0.53	0.26
Floor4Z2	0.34	0.27	0.48	0.25	0.59	0.25
Floor4Z4	0.28	0.25	0.29	0.24	0.53	0.24
Floor4Z5	0.36	0.18	0.35	0.23	0.46	0.17
Floor5Z1	0.23	0.2	0.19	0.15	0.45	0.22
Floor5Z2	0.29	0.19	0.28	0.19	0.35	0.19
Floor5Z4	0.33	0.36	0.31	0.3	0.58	0.3
Floor5Z5	0.43	0.26	0.29	0.31	0.64	0.26
Floor6Z1	0.26	0.23	0.25	0.29	0.37	0.22
Floor6Z2	0.36	0.28	0.22	0.28	0.38	0.3
Floor6Z4	0.26	0.17	0.27	0.22	0.41	0.21
Floor6Z5	0.47	0.22	0.26	0.23	0.58	0.23
Floor7Z1	0.34	0.28	0.43	0.31	0.65	0.48
Floor7Z2	0.31	0.3	0.59	0.33	0.61	0.23
Floor7Z4	0.28	0.21	0.28	0.23	0.41	0.2
Floor7Z5	0.44	0.38	0.71	0.34	0.61	0.36

TABLE I: Virtual Sensor Field Accuracy (L_s) with Spatial Grouping or predicting a cell using **columns from the same row**.

Zone	Power			Ambience		
	AC	Light	App	Temp	RH	Lux
Floor2Z1	0.08	0.07	0.11	0.25	0.14	0.05
Floor2Z2	0.09	0.06	0.13	0.24	0.25	0.09
Floor2Z4	0.09	0.06	0.12	0.26	0.66	0.06
Floor3Z1	0.11	0.03	0.08	0.04	0.26	0.03
Floor3Z2	0.07	0.04	0.09	0.05	0.17	0.03
Floor3Z4	0.09	0.03	0.11	0.06	0.23	0.03
Floor3Z5	0.08	0.03	0.1	0.07	0.18	0.05
Floor4Z1	0.08	0.03	0.08	0.06	0.16	0.05
Floor4Z2	0.06	0.02	0.11	0.05	0.44	0.04
Floor4Z4	0.07	0.02	0.08	0.05	0.22	0.05
Floor4Z5	0.14	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.36	0.06
Floor5Z1	0.15	0.03	0.13	0.06	0.2	0.08
Floor5Z2	0.08	0.03	0.09	0.07	0.29	0.04
Floor5Z4	0.17	0.03	0.09	0.06	0.17	0.04
Floor5Z5	0.07	0.05	0.12	0.05	0.13	0.04
Floor6Z1	0.12	0.04	0.08	0.04	0.25	0.13
Floor6Z2	0.27	0.03	0.08	0.06	0.19	0.32
Floor6Z4	0.14	0.04	0.1	0.06	0.26	0.09
Floor6Z5	0.1	0.04	0.09	0.12	0.3	0.09
Floor7Z1	0.64	0.05	0.12	0.08	0.36	0.08
Floor7Z2	0.08	0.05	0.08	0.09	0.5	0.14
Floor7Z4	0.07	0.03	0.09	0.08	0.35	0.03
Floor7Z5	0.08	0.03	0.08	0.09	0.63	0.05

TABLE II: Virtual Sensor Field Accuracy (L_d) with Domain Wise Grouping or predicting a cell using **rows from the same column**.

tions in a controlled thermal environment.

$$\begin{aligned}
L_s[z, d] &= \sum_{v \in A^c(g=z)} \frac{M^z[v, d]}{|A^c(g=z)|} \\
L_d[z, d] &= \sum_{v \in A^c(g=d)} \frac{M^d[v, z]}{|A^c(g=d)|}
\end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Due to lack of space, it is impossible to show all M^g tables, instead we report the spatial (L_s) and domain (L_d) wise loss to fill up Table I and II respectively. Amongst all the sensors, relative humidity is most difficult to approximate, L_s (min=0.37, max=0.66) and L_d (min=0.14, max=0.63) across all zones. Amongst the ambient sensors, luminosity (lux) levels has the best L_d (min=0.03, max=0.14) although for Floor 2 Zone 2, we observe $L_s = 0.06 > L_d = 0.09$. For, indoor temperature prediction L_d (min=0.04, max=0.14) is lower than L_s (min=0.19, max=0.71) for all floors except in floor 2 with zone 1 $L_s = 0.18, L_d = 0.25$ and zone 2 $L_s = 0.11, L_d = 0.24$. Power Consumption pattern is usually continuous but "non-differentiable" in nature arising due to sharp peaks and crests for fast response times. The ability to learn the patterns

from inter zonal power consumption $L_d =$ (min=0.03, max=0.27) is more effective rather using intra-zonal data sources $L_s =$ (min=0.2, max=0.71) for predicting light, AC, and appliance channels. Majorly, we see that domain wise grouping performs better on average which confirms the intuitiveness of being guessed *easily* by similar peers. For every type of sensor, the error matrix for ambient and power consumption sensors are visualised as a heatmap in Figures 7 and 8 respectively.

B. Baseline Comparison

We compare our approach with a similar type of problem that eliminates non redundant ones from a sensor set. For a fair comparison, we evaluate the value of the objective set $O = [O_b^v, O_f^v]$ at every solution point. The baseline algorithm starts with a signal decomposition step where instantaneous phase estimates (IP), instantaneous frequency estimates (IF), and instantaneous amplitude estimates (IA) are extracted per sensor. Unsupervised learning is applied to the Intrinsic Mode Function space

Market Segments	Ambiencer (QoS)	Power (QoS)
Home Solutions	DIY	DIY
Co Working Zones	Industrial	DIY
Community Spaces	DIY	Industrial
Commercial	Industrial	Industrial

TABLE III: Classification of Market Segmentation with hardware requirement types for monitoring.

spanned by (IP,IF,IA) to generate clusters. The parameter space for K-Means [16] is varied between $k \in [30, 90]$ and for DBSCAN [17] the range for minimum clubbing distance "eps" $\in [0.01, 0.04]$ and minimum number of samples $\in [6, 23]$. For every cluster, we take q candidate points and encode them as $\{0, 1\}$ and take the minimum $[O_b^v, O_f^v]$ obtained from spatially and domain wise encoding. Figure 4a shows the scatter plot between forward and backward translation errors for the baseline algorithms and our approach. The dual objective values from K-Means and DBSCAN converge to an error region of $(O_f^v, O_b^v \in [0.3 - 0.5])$ while the best solution yielded by evolutionary computing has $(O_f^v, O_b^v \in [0.20 - 0.25])$. In contrast to unsupervised learning, our algorithm generates a Pareto front as per Figure Fig 4a where no objective can decrease without increasing another. From Figure 4b, we observe that using $[60, 85]$ sensors, the forward translation MSE $\in [0.05, 0.1]$ with a backward margin between $[0.2, 0.25]$. Out of 138 sensors, the system achieves a fair trade-off between forward and backward translation MSE $[0.16, 0.19]$ with approximately 45 – 50% less sensors. Increasing number of observable sensors, decreases O_f^v to MSE $[0.05]$ using 80-85 sensors while the backward error O_b^v increases to 0.48 since more number of difficult sensor patterns have to be approximated now.

C. Segmented Business Trade-offs

We now study the effect of grouping with respect to the virtualization accuracy, monetary risk and energy foot-printing. Average cost is around $[10 - 20]\$$ for ambient sensors like humidity, temperature while smart meters can be expensive around $[50 - 100]\$$. We observe that the industrial or DIY embedded sensor hardware are typically between

(a) Baseline Comparison

(b) Dual Objective Optimization

Fig. 4: Algorithm Performance Comparison on bidirectional losses while approximating between Support and Approximated Sets.

$[10 - 25]$ Watts. Assuming 30 days a month, a 5W sensor will consume close to $5 \times 24 \times 30 = 3.6$ energy units (kWh) monthly. Industrial grade quality of smart sensor or power consumption meters can be more energy efficient but expensive than assembled Do-It-Yourself counterparts. Let the cost and energy consumption ratio between power meters and ambient sensor is given by $\frac{C_p}{C_{amb}} = \frac{P_{g \neq Amb}^r}{P_{g = Amb}^r}$ and $\frac{E_p}{E_{amb}} = \frac{P_{g \neq Amb}^w}{P_{g = Amb}^w}$. We meet the requirements of Table III through 2×2 factorial design with $\frac{C_p}{C_{amb}} \in \{1, 2.5\}$ and $\frac{E_p}{E_{amb}} \in \{1, 2\}$.

The system is able to pick up sensors to achieve

(a) Forward Accuracy

(b) Backward Translation Error

Fig. 5: Backward Translation Error of last generation candidates in the Building Chromosome Gene Pool.

a Virtual Sensor Field configuration under all 4 experimental conditions with a forward translation ($MSE \leq 0.2$). Figure 5 shows the distribution of $\{O_f^v, O_b^v\}$ for the optimised last generation gene pool where number of sensors vary from $[30, 96]$ and $\{O_f^v, O_b^v\}$ lies between $\{0.02, 1\}$. We see a natural affinity of the system to optimize the sensor field with minimal or less expensive sensor solution is evident from design spaces with high levels of backward MSE (> 0.6). The capital and operating cost of the smart building solution is approximated in Figure 6. We regress the best possible linear fit to approximate the rate of change of O_{energy}, O_{cost}

(a) Approximation of Bill of Materials

(b) Optimizing Energy Footprint

Fig. 6: Evaluation of last generation chromosomes on capital cost O_{cost} and operating energy footprint O_{energy} .

Market Segment	Monthly Energy (kWh)	Capital \$
Home	15	22.5
Community	11	26.6
Co-Working	8.8	24.5
Commercial	6.9	48.5

TABLE IV: Average Capital Cost and Monthly Energy Footprint for 4 different market segments

per additional sensor and fill up the entries of Tables IV with the fitted slope.

V. CONCLUSION

This work emphasized the role of spatio-temporal knowledge to bring down the operating cost of

building management system with an added layer of privacy. Generating a distributed virtual field contributes to the problem of monitoring spaces non intrusively. The virtual sensor field can be utilized to approximate the original data in case of sensor fault or turn off unnecessary permissible sensors. We observe that the missing sensor approximation can be kept competitively accurate with bidirectional power-ambience converters with explainable insights.

The extension of the work can be studying the Utopian sensor placement across zones with theoretical learning guarantees. It is interesting to evaluate the performance in an online learning setting which can be the next step towards auto updating spatio temporal models.

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(a) Temperature

(a) AC Power

(b) Luminosity levels

(b) Light Power

(c) Humidity

(c) Appliance Power Consumption

Fig. 7: Virtualization prediction on processing similar ambience channels as one group

Fig. 8: Virtualization prediction on treating identical type of power meters as one group